

COMPARISON OF ANTI-MICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY OF
AZITHROMYCIN AND LEVOFLOXACIN AGAINST *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*
AND *Salmonella typhi*

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Abstract

Background and Objective: It is a bleak reality that antibiotics resistance resulted in the death of thousands of individuals every year around the world. Therefore, the aim of current study was to compare the sensitivity and resistance patterns of two common bacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhi* against azithromycin and levofloxacin.

Methodology: An in-vitro comparative experimental study conducted in the Pharmaceutical Microbiology Lab., Faculty of Pharmacy, Hamdard University and Pathology Lab. of Husaini Hematology & Oncology Trust from May-2024 to October-2024. Collected isolates were 160; 75 (46.9%) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and 85 (53.1%) *Salmonella typhi*. These isolates have been obtained from blood, ear swabs, pus, urine and tracheal aspiration. Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method was used for the antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Results: Activity patterns of 15 mcg azithromycin (33.8%) and 5 mcg levofloxacin (66.2%) were noted; where 4 (2.5%) samples of *P. aeruginosa* exhibited sensitivity to azithromycin while 42 (26.3%) samples of *P. aeruginosa* showed sensitivity for levofloxacin. Meanwhile, 27 (16.9%) samples of *S. typhi* displayed as sensitive to azithromycin, but 28 (17.5%) samples *S. typhi* gave sensitive results towards levofloxacin. Mean zone of inhibition of *P. aeruginosa* was comparable ($t=-1.624$; $p=0.109$) by levofloxacin and azithromycin. However; for *S. typhi* levofloxacin was significantly better ($t=-11.415$; $p=0.0001$) compared to azithromycin.

Conclusion: The antimicrobial sensitivity of levofloxacin is higher than azithromycin. This clarifies that azithromycin should not be the first choice to treat infections against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. typhi*.

INTRODUCTION

It is a bleak reality that every year hundreds of thousands of humans die due to the widespread bacterial resistance to antibiotics. This issue was declared a major public health threat by the World

Health Organization (WHO) in 2014.[1] It has become essential to enhance the investment in the research pertaining to identify markers of resistance, development of new antimicrobial agents and

determine the role of bacteria in the transmission of antibiotic resistance to human and animal microbial flora.[1]

As one of the top three causes of opportunistic infections in humans, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is a gram-negative pathogen capable of causing severe acute and chronic infections; these life-threatening infections—such as pneumonia, meningitis, and urinary tract infections—are a particular danger to immunocompromised individuals, including those with cystic fibrosis.[2] It also commonly spoils foods that are high in moisture and nutrients.[2] As a common resident of humid environments, it poses a serious risk for the contamination of drinking water.[2] Despite being widely known, *P. aeruginosa* is under-recognized in food safety areas. Owing to its pronounced metabolic versatility, rapid replication rate, considerable adaptive potential, and psychrotrophic capabilities, this bacterium is ubiquitous and a leading etiological agent of foodborne disease.[3] *P. aeruginosa* can grow in cold temperatures (4–6°C), which is why it is classified as a psychrophilic bacterium.[4] In developing countries like Pakistan, sepsis is taken as the cause of about 75% of deaths of burn patients; a study demonstrates a high level of the occurrence of *P. aeruginosa* in wounds of burn patients with nearly half of the bacterial isolates being MDR (Multi-Drug Resistant).[5] Regrettably, the widespread and indiscriminate use of antibiotics has led to the development of significant resistance in this pathogen.[2]

Salmonella typhi, a gram-negative, anaerobic bacillus, belonging to the family *Enterobacteriaceae*, transmits enteric fever to humans via person-to-person contact as it doesn't have a significant animal reservoir.[6] It is transmitted via contaminated human feces usually by means of contaminated water.[6] Enteric fever, encompassing both typhoid and paratyphoid fever, is a significant bacterial illness responsible for substantial morbidity and mortality, with the highest burden in developing nations of Asia, Africa, and South America.[6] It is associated with improper sanitary measures and drinkable water sources.[6] Enteric fever can be clinically manifested by high grade fever, headache, fatigue, painful muscles, constipation, abdominal pain, vomiting along with

some other symptoms.[7] It can be deadly, when results in septicemia or meningitis.[7] The interval of fever and severity of the disease depend upon the type of bacterial strains and host immune responses.[8] Typhoid and paratyphoid fevers are clinically same except the severity of the complications; although typhoid fever is more ubiquitous than paratyphoid fever in most endemic areas.[8] Across many parts of Asia and Africa, the most prevalent multidrug-resistant (MDR) *S. Typhi* strain identified is haplotype-58 (H58).[8] Travel-associated XDR *S. Typhi* infections have been identified in multiple countries, demonstrating its rapid spread across the globe.[8] A considerable population (2–5%) of recovered patients becomes asymptomatic chronic carriers for years.[8] Unfortunately in Pakistan, the rate of typhoid caused by MDR and XDR *S. typhi* is very high.[9, 10] In 2016, the first case of XDR *S. typhi* was reported in Karachi.[9, 10] After the first breakout in Sindh, >17,000 cases of XDR typhoid were brought up.[9, 10] In 2016–2017, >800 cases of XDR typhoid were notified only in Hyderabad, naming the entire area endemic.[9, 10] In those times, spread of infections with XDR typhoid to other non-endemic countries has been usually associated with travellers from these areas. Passengers who couldn't assure safe food and water intake and receive vaccines before travel, omitted their risk of spreading enteric fever.[9, 10]

The objective of this research article was to assess the sensitivity and resistance patterns of two commonly prescribed antibiotics i.e. azithromycin and levofloxacin in the infections caused by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhi*. The study will also help to determine the prevalence of infections in Karachi, that are caused by these bacteria. Another aim of study was to compare antibiotics that can be prescribed as a therapeutic choice in dealing with appropriate infections or that can contribute in lowering the increasing number of treatment failures at such local level.

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted from October 27, 2024, to March 7, 2025, at two sites in Karachi, Pakistan: Pharmaceutical Microbiology Laboratory (Department of Pharmaceutics, Faculty of Pharmacy)

and the Husaini Hematology and Oncology Trust. A collection of 160 clinical isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (75 isolates) and *Salmonella typhi* (85 isolates) was assembled. Initial strain identification was performed by examining key morphological characteristics of colonies.

Ethical Approval: Current study is approved by Ethical Review Committee of Hamdard University, Karachi, Pakistan. Approval number is ERC-FOP-2024-05.

Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI) Guidelines: Antimicrobial resistance was evaluated by Kirby-Bauers Disk Diffusion Method, following the 2015 guidelines facilitated by Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI).[11] The Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) is responsible for updating and modifying the original procedure of Kirby and Bauer through a global consensus process.(Table 1) Bacterial inocula were prepared using the direct colony suspension method. Bacterial suspensions were prepared in tryptone soy broth (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK; Cat. No. CM0129).

Kirby-Bauers Disk Diffusion Method: 8 mol/L BaCl₂ (1.175 % w/v BaCl₂.2H₂O) was added to 99.5 mL of 0.18 mol/L (0.36 N) H₂SO₄ (1% v/v) with a thorough mixing so that a proper suspension is made.[12] The density of the suspension was assessed with the help of a spectrophotometer employing 1 cm light path and corresponding cuvettes. It was ensured that the absorbance of prepared 0.5 McFarland Standard lying within the values of 0.08-0.13 at a wavelength of 625 nm.[12]

For the growth of organisms, tryptone soya broth (Oxoid CM337) was used. At 37°C, the incubation of all tubes was executed so that the pre-requisite turbidity similar to that of 0.5 McFarland standard is achieved.[13]

After 15 min of incubation and its turbidity adjustment, a sterile cotton swab was dipped in the suspension of bacterium inoculum and quickly placed beside the test tube walls exactly above the level of fluid and the extra fluid was wiped down. The swabs were streaked thrice on the whole Mueller-Hilton Agar (MHA) (CM0337 Oxoid UK) surface in every direction.[12, 14]

In the study, azithromycin 15 mcg (Oxoid UK) and levofloxacin 5 mcg (Oxoid UK) discs were used. With the help of sterile forceps, the antibiotics discs were placed on the surface of agar medium keeping a distance of 24 mm (taken from the center) among all discs and a distance of 12 mm was kept between the edges of petri dish plate and the disc.[12, 15]

Incubation was carried out at 34–36°C for 16–20 hours with plates positioned agar side up. Zone diameters were then measured to the nearest millimeter using a vernier caliper as per Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI) protocols. All this bench work has been done inside the laminar airflow hood and within the vicinity of bunsen burner.[15]

When the period of incubation was over, the inspection of plates was done to witness the proper growth of the cultured isolate, also ensuring no contamination. The clear zones of inhibition around the antibiotic discs were observed and their diameters were measured by *mm = millimeter

Data analysis: Data was analyzed by SPSS-22 version and MS-EXCEL software. Descriptive statistics determined the frequency and proportions of microorganisms. Independent sample t-test was applied to compare the mean zone of inhibitions of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhi* by azithromycin and levofloxacin. The level of significance was 5%.

RESULTS

160 clinical isolates have been evaluated; where 75 (46.9%) were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and 85 (53.1%) were *Salmonella typhi*. These isolates have been obtained from different specimens of patients, including 100 (62.5%) from blood, 7 (4.4%) from ear swabs, 26 (16.3%) from pus, 25 (15.6%) from urine culture and 2 (1.3%) from tracheal aspiration causing various infections.

Activity patterns of one hundred and sixty (160) clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa* (75) and *S. typhi* (85) were evaluated using azithromycin 15 mcg (54) 33.8% and levofloxacin 5 mcg (106) 66.3% and the results were noted; where 4 samples of *P. aeruginosa* (2.5%)

Table 1: Antibiotics Sensitivity Standard Criteria [13]

Antimicrobial Agents	Disc Content	Name of microbe	Interpretive Criteria for Zone of Inhibition (mm*)		
			Susceptible	Intermediate	Resistant
Azithromycin	15 mcg	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	≥ 18	14 - 17	≤ 13
		<i>S. typhi</i>	≥ 13	N/A**	≤ 12
Levofloxacin	5 mcg	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	≥ 17	14 - 16	≤ 13
		<i>S. typhi</i>	≥ 31	21 - 30	≤ 20

*mm=millimeter; **N/A=Not applicable in guidelines

exhibited sensitivity, 3 samples of clinical isolates (1.9%) gave intermediate response while 5 samples (3.1%) showed resistance against azithromycin. On the contrary, 42 samples (26.3%) of *P. aeruginosa* showed sensitivity for levofloxacin, 7 samples (4.4%) exhibited an intermediate response and 14 (8.8%) were resistant. Meanwhile, 27 samples of *S. typhi* (16.9%) were sensitive to azithromycin, none of the isolates turned out to give intermediate response but 15 samples (9.4%) exhibited resistance. On the other hand, 28 samples (17.5%) of *S. typhi* gave sensitive

results for levofloxacin, 6 samples (3.8%) had an intermediate response and 9 (5.6%) exhibited resistance. Levofloxacin turned out to be the most sensitive of both tested antibiotics however, resistance has developed against it as well. (Table 2; Figure 1)

Mean zone of inhibition of *P. aeruginosa* was comparable ($t=-1.624$; $p=0.109$) by levofloxacin and azithromycin. However; for *S. typhi* levofloxacin was significantly better ($t=-11.415$; $p=0.0001$) compared to azithromycin. (Table 3)

Table 2: Activity patterns of clinical isolates against antibiotics

Susceptible Patterns			
Pathogen	Antibiotic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Azithromycin	4	2.5
	Levofloxacin	42	26.3
<i>S. typhi</i>	Azithromycin	27	16.9
	Levofloxacin	28	17.5
Intermediate Patterns			
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Azithromycin	3	1.9
	Levofloxacin	7	4.4
<i>S. typhi</i>	Levofloxacin	6	3.8
Resistance Patterns			
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Azithromycin	5	3.1
	Levofloxacin	14	8.8
<i>S. typhi</i>	Azithromycin	15	9.4
	Levofloxacin	9	5.6

Figure 1: Compiled activity of antibiotics against isolates

Table 3: Comparison of zone of inhibitions of antibiotics against isolates

Name of microbe	Antimicrobial Agents	Mean zone of inhibition	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-test	p-value
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Azithromycin	15.7500	±5.31	±1.533	-1.624	0.109
	Levofloxacin	18.6349	±5.69	±0.717		
<i>Salmonella Typhi</i>	Azithromycin	15.0714	±3.93	±0.607	-11.415	0.0001
	Levofloxacin	28.2326	±6.38	±0.972		

DISCUSSION

The core purpose of this study was to evaluate present-day activity of 15 mcg azithromycin (33.8%) and 5mcg levofloxacin (66.2%) against strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* & *Salmonella typhi*. Antibiotics have to pass through the bacterial membrane to produce effects on intracellular targets but *P. aeruginosa* has limited outer membrane penetrability.[16] As a result, there is shortage of porins in the outer membrane of *P. aeruginosa*. [16] Porins normally transport nutrients across the membrane and stabilize it.[16] In the current scenario; there is increase trend of antibiotic resistance in *S.typhi* cases.[17] Hence, typhoid has evolved into a universal health problem.[17] Many aspects have been involved in its development, prominently; mechanisms of efflux pumps, persistent cell formation, neutralization of enzymes and the formation of biofilms.[17] In *S.typhi* infections, biofilms in particular have played a significant role in

the rise of antibiotic resistance; which prevented the penetration of antibiotics and act as a challenging barrier.[17]

The results of the current study revealed that both organisms i.e. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhi* were highly prevalent in blood samples compared to other sites of body. Although they cause infections at different sites of human body; nonetheless, both organisms mostly found in blood samples obtained from pathological laboratories. Nasrin *et al* states that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, being an opportunistic pathogen produces acute lethal infections to immune-compromised patients throughout the world.[18] It is usually a reason of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs).[18] This is in agreement with another study in which Ishida *et al*, has laid emphasis on the *P. aeruginosa*'s biofilm-forming ability in cystic fibrosis (CF) patients and chronic pulmonary infections.[19] A study carried out in 2021 by Elborn *et al*, in Europe and Canada,

inhaled solution of levofloxacin has been approved for the treatment of chronic pulmonary infections caused due to *P. aeruginosa*, especially in CF patients.[20] At high concentrations, the topical use of levofloxacin lowers the systemic exposure of the drug, efficiently enters the biofilms and manage chronic pulmonary infections caused due to *P. aeruginosa*. [20] The another study documented enhanced antimicrobial activity of levofloxacin by including it into lipid nanocarriers (LNCs); which supported the antibiofilm effectiveness of an o/w levofloxacin emulsion of peppermint oil.[21]

As far as activity patterns of clinical isolates; current study has shown 26.3% sensitivity of levofloxacin against *P. aeruginosa* while azithromycin was only 2.5% sensitive; in addition levofloxacin was 17.5% sensitive against *S. typhi* but azithromycin has revealed 16.9% sensitivity.(Table 2) These findings of current study are consistent with the findings of other studies conducted in different parts of the world. According to Xu *et al* in 2024, to hinder antimicrobial penetration, *P. aeruginosa* is able to develop enough resistance to most of the first-line antimicrobials and form a biofilm resulting in complex pseudomonal diseases.[22] In 2021, Leroy mentioned the *in-vitro* inactivity of azithromycin against *P. aeruginosa*. [23] Azithromycin revealed virulence-suppressing effect *in-vitro* and virulence-reducing activity *in-vivo*. [23] If there are fewer chances for drug interactions, it can be used as an adjunct for the management of *P. aeruginosa* pneumonia.[23] Regarding *S. typhi*; a cross-sectional study, compared the genomic aspects of different isolates of *S. typhi* from Bangladesh, Pakistan, Nepal and an endemic region in the North of India; [24] in this study azithromycin-resistant isolates collected in India were genetically different from the ones reported from Bangladesh, Pakistan and Nepal.[24] In order to treat enteric fever in South Asia, increased dependence on azithromycin emerged to impel resistance.[24] This might have been facilitated by interactions with fluoroquinolone-resistant mutations.[24]

When zones of inhibition are compared in current study; it was observed that levofloxacin was significantly better ($t=-11.415$; $p=0.0001$) compared to azithromycin for *Salmonella typhi* infection. In contrast to this, the zone of inhibition of

Pseudomonas aeruginosa with both antibiotics was comparable and turned out to be non-significant ($t=-1.624$; $p=0.109$). (Table 3) From the latter results, it can be concluded that azithromycin and levofloxacin can be equally effective drugs for the treatment of chronic infections caused by *Salmonella typhi*.

Interestingly; a study was carried out regarding self-medication in 3 tertiary-care hospitals in Karachi by Shaikh *et al*. [25] This study proved that just like other developing countries, availability of antibiotics in Pakistan is easily possible without a prescription, relating to the mis-use of antibiotics, which further causing increased resistance of antibiotics within the country.[25] Therefore; the situation is alarming in Karachi due to resistance patterns observed by both organisms against azithromycin and levofloxacin.

CONCLUSION

The conclusive results of the current study show that the antibacterial sensitivity of levofloxacin is greater than azithromycin. Azithromycin is not the first choice to treat the illnesses caused by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhi* because results revealed 3.1% and 9.4% resistance against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. typhi* respectively. In comparison, levofloxacin is the preferable antimicrobial to treat ailments produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhi* as it exhibited 26.3% sensitivity against *P. aeruginosa* and 17.5% susceptibility to *S. typhi*. However, it should be realized that this research requires additional studies; emphasizing on the optimum use of antimicrobials along with regular analysis of bacterial activity in order to prevent our local population from bacterial resistance not only in Karachi, but also different parts of country.

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DECLARATIONS

Competing Interests

All authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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